

Applications of Quantum Dots in Nanoelectronics and Plasmonics

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This talk will describe how quantum dots can be utilized to build monochromatic image processors that can perform simple image processing algorithms such as edge detection, horizontal line detection (Fig. 1), and vertical line detection. Further, by using quantum dots with multi-peak tunneling characteristics, color image processing algorithms can be implemented to perform more complex image functions like quantization effect (Fig. 2), color extraction (Fig. 3), shifting (Fig. 4), and so on.

The talk will also briefly discuss the architecture of a quantum dot based velocity tuned filter that can perform motion detection algorithms as shown in Fig. 5, where the stationary target object, shown in red and yellow color, can be detected against the background of other moving objects. Complete details of this new architecture are provided in an accompanying paper in the IEEE NANO-06 proceedings.

Finally, the talk will briefly discuss a theoretical framework to explain the surface plasmon dynamics of a single metallic nano-particle (Fig. 6) and a linear array of metallic nano-particles (Fig. 7).

Fig. 1. Vertical line detection application of the QD network.

Fig. 2. 4X4 color image quantization simulation results

Fig. 3. White color extraction. (a) Initialized with one color value in the filter dots; (b) Initialized with input image color value in the filter dots.

Fig. 4. Simulation result of shift function with transient response from 0 ns to 1 ns.

Fig. 5: Experimental result of velocity tuned filter for a velocity of 0 pixel/second : (a) input moving image, (b) output filtered image.

Fig. 6. These plots show the electric scattering field E_z in the XY plane ($Z = 500$ nm) when the incident plane waves with different energies irradiates only Au nanoparticles. The plane wave with z-polarized electric field is irradiating the first Au sphere for a long time. This plane wave propagates in the x-direction with different frequencies.

Fig. 7. The optical pulse propagation in the plasmon waveguide with resonance frequency in terms of various guiding ratios: 1/2, 1/4, 1/6, and 1/8.

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